

Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes. Outer Ion Effect on Magnesium Halide Complexes of Ammonia, Pyridine and Ethylenediamine

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A number of adducts of magnesium halide with neutral donor ligands, ammonia, pyridine and ethylenediamine, have been synthesised ($MgCl_2 \cdot 6NH_3$, $MgBr_2 \cdot 6NH_3$, $MgI_2 \cdot 6NH_3$, $MgCl_2 \cdot 4Py$, $MgBr_2 \cdot 2Py$, $MgI_2 \cdot 2Py$, $MgCl_2 \cdot 3en$, $MgBr_2 \cdot 2en$ and $MgI_2 \cdot 2en$) and the outer ion effect on the donor properties of these ligands have been looked into. Infrared studies suggest that ethylenediamine acts as a *trans*-bridging ligand between two magnesium ions in these adducts.

LITERATURE survey shows that very little systematic work has been done on magnesium halide-ammonia, -pyridine and -ethylenediamine complexes¹⁻³. We have synthesised a number of adducts of magnesium halide with these neutral donor ligands, with a view to make a comparative study of the coordinating ability of these ligands towards magnesium ion.

In ammonia complexes, outer ions play a dominant role, and influence the stability of the complexes. Infrared spectral bands of N—H and M—N shift due to hydrogen bonding; N—H band stretch decreases, whereas deformation and rocking frequencies increase. Far-infrared studies point out that M—O and M—N bonds are quite strong. M—N bond strength have been found to be greatest for chloride and least for iodide.

Experimental

Our usual method of synthesis was to place a weighed amount of anhydrous magnesium halide in

a desiccator, charged with the ligand, which gave these neutral ligands a better chance of coordination with magnesium halide.

In case of adducts of ethylenediamine with anhydrous magnesium halide, the reactions were carried out in ethanolic medium also. Anhydrous magnesium halide was dissolved in absolute ethanol and ethylenediamine was added dropwise. The adducts, which separated out immediately were filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 90°.

Results and Discussion

All these adducts are stable in dry air but decompose rapidly when exposed to moist air. In non-polar solvents, these adducts are insoluble. The colour, transition/decomposition temperatures and analytical values of the compounds are given in Table 1.

All the three hexa-aquo magnesium salts lose water molecules at high temperatures. Only two

TABLE 1

Compd.	Colour	Transition/ decomposition temp. (t) °C	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	M	Hal
$MgCl_2 \cdot 6NH_3$	White	—	—	—	41.9 (42.6)	11.8 (12.2)	35.3 (36.04)
$MgI_2 \cdot 3en$	Pale yellow	170–172	25.7 (26.18)	8.1 (8.7)	29.8 (30.6)	8.3 (8.7)	25.1 (25.8)
$MgCl_2 \cdot 4py$	White	160	57.8 (58.5)	4.3 (4.8)	13.0 (13.6)	5.2 (5.8)	16.8 (17.3)
$MgBr_2 \cdot 6NH_3$	White	—	—	—	28.6 (29.3)	8.0 (8.4)	54.9 (55.7)
$MgBr_2 \cdot 2en$	Pale yellow	175	15.2 (15.7)	4.8 (5.2)	17.8 (18.4)	7.3 (7.9)	51.8 (52.6)
$MgBr_2 \cdot 2py$	White	172	34.6 (35.1)	2.7 (2.9)	7.6 (8.2)	6.8 (7.0)	46.0 (46.8)
$MgI_2 \cdot 6NH_3$	White	—	—	—	21.6 (22.1)	5.4 (6.0)	65.9 (66.8)
$MgI_2 \cdot 2en$	Pale yellow	176–178	11.6 (12.06)	3.8 (4.0)	13.7 (14.0)	5.7 (6.0)	62.9 (63.8)
$MgI_2 \cdot 2py$	White	176–178	26.8 (27.5)	2.1 (2.3)	6.0 (6.4)	5.0 (5.4)	57.0 (57.9)

water molecules can be removed when $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ is heated above 130° . This indicates that water molecule in the hydrated salt are bonded strongly to the metal atom. In case of anhydrous magnesium chloride, three molecules of ethylenediamine are present inside the coordination sphere, indicating thereby, that the chloride ions are in simple ionic form. However, in case of magnesium bromide and iodide, only two molecules of ethylenediamine are attached to magnesium ion; the remaining secondary valencies of magnesium in these complexes may be satisfied either by bromide and iodide ions, respectively, or the complexes may be four-coordinated. This can be attributed to the fact that as the size of the anion increases, its electron donating tendencies also increases, and consequently bromide, as well as iodide ions get coordinated to the central metal atom. In ammonia complexes of the three halogens, six molecules of ammonia are attached to the metal, indicating that the halide ions are not inside the coordination sphere. On the contrary, complexes of anhydrous magnesium chloride with six pyridine molecules cannot be isolated. This may be due to the steric factor. Also, as the size of halogen atom increases, it hinders the approach of pyridine molecule. This is evident from the decreasing trend of chelating ability of $MgCl_2$, $MgBr_2$ and MgI_2 for pyridine

Infrared measurements: The absorptions of these hydrated salts, in the lower infrared region show that these are not simple lattice water. In conformity with the transition metal aquo complexes^{4,5}, these also show rocking vibrations at $705-722\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and wagging at $440-520\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $MgCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, M—O stretches have been identified near 360 cm^{-1} (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Compd.	$\rho_r (H_2O)$	$\rho_w (H_2O)$	ν_{M-O}
$MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	710	440	363
$MgBr_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	722	470	
$MgI_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	720	495	
$MgCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$	705	520	360

The spectra of magnesium halide-ammonia complexes are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Complexes	$\nu_{as} (NH_3)$	$\nu_s (NH_3)$	$\delta_{as} (HNH)$	$\delta_s (HNH)$	$\rho_r (NH_3)$	ν_{M-N}
$[Mg(NH_3)_6] X_2$ where X =						
Cl	3353	3210	1603	1170	660	363
Br	3370	3200	1590	1160	640	370
I	3390	3200	1610	1150	615	320
ClO_4	3400		1620	1150	620	
$[Mg(NH_3)_4(H_2O)_2]Cl_2$			1610	1175	660	370

The NH_3 stretching frequencies of these complexes are lower than those of the free ammonia molecules. This may be due to two factors, the effect of coordination and the effect of outer ions. In cobalt(III) amine complexes⁶ NH_3 stretching

frequencies of the chloride, bromide and iodide are lower than that of the perchlorate. This has been attributed to the weakening of the N—H bond due to the formation of the N—H...Cl type hydrogen bond. The effects of coordination, and hydrogen bonding mentioned above, also shift the NH_3 deformation and rocking modes to higher frequencies. The N—H stretching frequencies decrease, while the deformation and rocking frequencies increase.

It is concluded from the observations that the hydrogen bonding between N—H bond and the outer ion becomes stronger in the order of I^- , Br^- and Cl^- salts. The M—N stretching bands for the chloride, bromide, iodide and aquo-chloride, show up at 363 , 330 , 320 and 370 cm^{-1} , respectively and the relative strength of the bond order is $H_2O \cdot Cl > Cl > Br > I$.

An examination of the infrared spectra of magnesium halide-ethylenediamine complexes shows that all the four principal regions of absorption, ~ 3300 (stretching mode), ~ 1600 (asymmetric deformation), ~ 1300 (symmetric deformation) and $\sim 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (rocking) for NH_2 are present in the complexes. Over and above, the vibrations of the CH_2 group ~ 1360 (bend), ~ 1280 (wag), ~ 1010 (skeleton) and $\sim 720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (rock), can also be spotted out.

The two N—H stretching vibrations appear as medium peaks between 3340 and 3250 cm^{-1} . The 3377 cm^{-1} band of en remains unaffected after complexation, but the 3316 cm^{-1} band is very much affected in the complexes. This appears at $\sim 3250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with reduced intensity in the complexes, thereby suggesting that there has been decrease in the bond order of N—H on complexation. These halide complexes in conformity with a *trans*-structure show two sharp peaks at 1155 and 1115 cm^{-1} for the chloride, and 1150 and 1110 cm^{-1} for the iodide; three peaks are shown for bromide at 1155 , 1110 and 1095 cm^{-1} , and same for the $MgCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$. en (1156 , 1115 and 1105 cm^{-1}). The *cis*-complex with halide ions show usually a group of four bands in this region⁷.

The *trans*-complexes of en show three strong bands in the far-infrared region ($604-510\text{ cm}^{-1}$)⁸.

In the magnesium halide complexes, the chloride shows only two bands at 515 and 482 cm^{-1} , whereas the bromide (530 sh, 510 , 475 cm^{-1}), iodide (510 , 500 and 480 cm^{-1}) and aquo-chloride (530 , 515 and 482 cm^{-1}) show only three bands. These bands are

evenly distributed in that region. A *cis*-isomer would have given at least four bands and the pattern of the bands are also different, three clustered together and one further removed.

Upon complex formation the pyridine (py) vibrations in the high frequency region are not shifted appreciably, whereas those at 604 (in-plane ring deformation) and 405 cm^{-1} (out of plane ring deformation) are shifted to higher frequencies. In magnesium chloride-py complex, the above two bands are well shifted to higher frequencies (605 and 425 cm^{-1}) suggesting that py molecules are coordinated to magnesium and similar observations are noted for MgBr_2 -Py (605 and 420 cm^{-1}) and MgI_2 -py (655 and 410 cm^{-1}). For $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -py, two broad bands are observed at 645 and 460 cm^{-1} .

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